

The High Temperature Volatilization of Thallic Oxide

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The high temperature behaviour of thallic oxide obtained from different source materials was studied thermogravimetrically. Initially the normal equilibrium reactions viz. (a) the dissociation of the solid Tl_2O_3 to Tl_2O or a $Tl_2O-Tl_2O_3$ solid solution and (b) the volatilization of the solid decomposition product, occur almost simultaneously. It has been observed that depending upon the experimental conditions, viz. the heating rate, the material of the crucible and the state of dispersion of sample, an additional reaction takes place. This is due to the vaporization of the still unreacted but molten Tl_2O_3 .

These reactions though not clearly distinguishable in the direct thermogravimetric curve, are unambiguously resolved in differential thermogravimetry (D.T.G) plots and in confirmatory DTA runs. The effects of the various experimental parameters on the TG and DTG curves are discussed.

During the course of a separate thermogravimetric study of the thallium thorium double carbonate [$3Tl_2CO_3 \cdot Th(CO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$] and of thallic carbonate¹, it was observed that the final weight loss in the range of 590 to 900° corresponded to the total thallic oxide formed as a product of earlier decompositions. In both cases it was also observed that thallic oxide (confirmed by X-rays) was deposited as a black condensate at the cooler end of the furnace. This suggested that the thallic oxide was simply volatilizing.

However, the differential thermogravimetric (D.T.G.) plot obtained from these T.G. curves, as also the D.T.A. curve showed three distinct peaks in the same temperature region. This indicated that thallic oxide was not undergoing simple volatilization, but that multiple reactions were taking place. Also, whatever may be the nature of the volatile reaction product, on cooling the thallic oxide was being reformed.

It was therefore decided to compare the high temperature behaviour of pure thallic oxide with that observed for thallic oxide formed *in situ* as a decomposition product. The influence of experimental factors, such as, heating rate, material of the sample holder and state of dispersion of the sample, was also evaluated.

1. S. H. Daroowalla—M.Sc. thesis on 'The study of some carbonates of thorium'—University of Bombay, 1965. *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 729.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Thallic Oxide

(i) Tl_2O_3 (I) was obtained by the *in situ* oxidation of the thallic oxide formed by the thermolysis of thallic carbonate (Johnson Matthey-Batch No. 7) in the temperature range 350 to 450°.

(ii) Tl_2O_3 (II) was obtained by the *in situ* oxidation of thallic oxide formed during the thermolysis of the thallium-thorium double carbonate.

(iii) Tl_2O_3 (III) was prepared by heating thallic carbonate (same as in (i) above) in air to 500° in a muffle furnace. The formation of Tl_2O_3 was confirmed by X-ray diffractometry.

Thermal Analysis.

Thermograms were obtained on a Stanton thermobalance of 1 mg. sensitivity, while the DTA curves were recorded on an instrument built by Deshpande and Karkhanavala², thermograms were obtained using heating rates of 6° and 2° per minute. Platinum and alumina crucibles were used.

X-ray diffraction.

The X-ray diffractometer patterns were recorded using the Philips automatic wide angle diffractometer (PW 1050) and filtered $CuK\alpha$ radiation (34kV, 18mA) from the Philips fully stabilized PW 1010 X-ray generator.

R E S U L T S

A typical T.G. curve for Tl_2O_3 (III) [heating rate: 6°/min.; Pt. crucible] is

Fig. 1. Tracing of T.G. curve of Tl_2O_3 (III)

shown in fig. 1. In the case of Tl_2O_3 (I) and (II) the earlier decomposition steps were also recorded. The differential thermogravimetry (D.T.G.) plots constructed from the T.G. recordings are shown in figs. 2, 3 and 4. The results are tabulated in Table I. The D.T.A. curves for Tl_2O_3 (I) and (II) obtained with a heating rate of 6°/min. are shown in fig. 5 (A) and (B).

TABLE I

Source Material	Thalious carbonate Tl ₂ O ₃ (I)				Thallium thorium double carbonate Tl ₂ O ₃ (II)				Thallic oxide Tl ₂ O ₃ (III)			
	6		2		6		2		6		2	
Rate of heating °C/min.	6		2		6		2		6		2	
Crucible material	Al ₂ O ₃	Pt	Al ₂ O ₃	Pt	Al ₂ O ₃	Pt	Al ₂ O ₃	Pt	Al ₂ O ₃	Pt	Al ₂ O ₃	Pt
Temp. (°C) (from D.T.G)	6		2		6		2		6		2	
1st peak	690±3	685±3	670±3	680±3	740±3	750±3	740±3	745±3	760±3	780±3	740±3	745±3
2nd peak	720 to 750	730 to 790	705 to 750	710 to 735	780 to 850	815 to 865	770 to 800	780 to 805	800 to 850	825 to 875	765 to 800	775
3rd peak	805±3	815±3	805±3	805±3	875±3	890±3	820±3	830±3	885±3	900±3	825±3	840±3
Overall reaction °C (from T.G.)	590 to 950	570 to 920	560 to 870	560 to 870	580 to 970*	600 to 970*	580 to 970*	590 to 970*	650 to 975	650 to 975	600 to 860	600 to 860

* Weight loss not complete due to slow release from sintered ThO₂ residue.

Table I—The maximum temperatures of the three D.T.G. peaks from various source materials.

DISCUSSION

High Temperature Behaviour of Tl₂O₃

There is scanty information on the high temperature behaviour of thallic oxide.

Duncan³ in 1929, Rassa⁴ in 1953 and Toropova and Pogorelyi⁵ in 1961 studied by tensometric method the decomposition of thallic oxide at temperatures upto 700°. (Duncan³ has studied upto 770°). Duval et al⁶ have merely reported that when Tl₂O₃ is heated the molecular species volatilizing is Tl₂O. Rassa⁴ has also reported that in vacuum Tl₂O₃ begins to decompose around 400° to Tl₂O and later the solid Tl₂O vaporizes which condenses on the cooler side of the tube.

The equilibrium oxygen pressures measured at different temperatures by Rassa⁴ and by Toropova and Pogorelyi⁵ are not concordant.

Also the results for the heating and cooling cycles are not very reproducible. This has been attributed to the formation of a series of solid solution between Tl₂O and Tl₂O₃.

Interpretation of the DTG curves

It could therefore be assumed that in air, the tendency of the thallic oxide to decompose to thalious oxide and oxygen, would be counterbalanced by the reoxidation of the thalious oxide. The overall reaction and therefore the coexistence of Tl₂O₃ and Tl₂O would depend on the rate constants for the forward and the backward reactions.

3. A. B. F. Duncan, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2697.

4. M. Rassa, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1953, **8**, 755.

5. T. G. Toropova and A. D. Pogorelyi, *Tr. Severo-Kavkazsk. Gornomet Inst.* 1961, **17**, 38.

6. C. Duval, C. Wadier and Y. Servigne, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1959, **20**, 263.

If as suggested by Rassa¹ the Ti_2O_3 and Ti_2O react to form a continuous series of solid-solution, then the situation would become considerably more complex. The volatilizing species could therefore be either Ti_2O_3 , Ti_2O or the solid solution. In case the volatilizing species is any one of the last two or both, these would have to later undergo reoxidation to Ti_2O_3 at lower temperatures since the deposit found in the cooler end of the furnace is proved to be Ti_2O_3 . This last reoxidation would however be outside the sample chamber and therefore cannot contribute to either the T.G. or D.T.A. curves.

On the above basis two peaks in the D.T.G. and D.T.A. curves corresponding to the following reactions, can be expected.

Since in separate experiments, it was found that the melting point of Ti_2O_3 (720°) lies within the temperature range studied. The additional endothermic peak in

Fig. 2 D.T.G. curve of $\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_3(\text{l})$ —The heating rate in degrees/min and the crucible material are indicated in bracket.

Fig. 3. D.T.G. curve of Ti_2O_3 (II) The heating rate in degrees/min and the crucible material are indicated in bracket.

Fig. 4. D.T.G. curve of Ti_2O_3 (III) The heating rate in degrees/min and the crucible material are indicated in bracket.

Fig. 5 (A) D. T. A. curve of Tl_2O_3 (I)
(B) D. T. A. curve of Tl_2O_3 (II)

the D.T.A. could possibly be attributed to melting, but this would not be able to explain the three peaks observed in the D.T.G.

The only other possibility is that since both TG and DTA are dynamic methods in which the temperature increases steadily, the reaction may not get adequate time to be completed. Hence under this non-equilibrium condition, additional reaction could be observed. From an analysis of DTG curves it is concluded that this assumption is correct and the third peak is due to the volatilization of the yet undecomposed but molten Tl_2O_3 .

Assignment of Peaks.

The D.T.G. plots (figs. 2, 3, 4) and Table I reveal the following characteristics of the various peaks:—

- the maximum temperatures of the first and third DTG peaks remain reasonably constant for each sample and are not markedly affected by changes in heating rate or crucible material;
- the maximum temperature for the second peak varies considerably and is markedly affected by changes in heating rates and crucible material; in fact there is a tendency for the second peak to split into a number of smaller ones (fig. 3B);
- the maximum temperatures of the first and third peaks are reproducible within normal experimental error ($\pm 3^\circ$);
- the maximum temperatures of the second group of peaks varies considerably in duplicate runs;
- the maximum temperature of the first peak varies with the source material, being lowest for Tl_2O_3 (I) and almost the same for Tl_2O_3 (II)

and (III) particularly at the slower heating rate. Yet the temperature of inception the reaction is lower for Tl_2O (I) and (II) than for Tl_2O_3 (III). This induction period is maximum for Tl_2O_3 (II);

- (f) the relative intensity of the second group of peak varies directly with that of the first peak; whilst the relative intensity of the third peak varies inversely with that of the first.

Considering these facts, the first peak is assigned to Reaction I. It cannot be due to Reaction II, because Reaction I has to precede it. It cannot also be due to Reaction III, because the existence of an induction period, as well as small weight loss and hence low relative intensity in DTG^{*}, are expected for the decomposition reaction but not for the volatilization reaction. Further the temperature region in which the peak occurs is consistent with the decomposition temperatures reported by earlier investigators for similar partial pressures of oxygen.

The second group of peaks can be attributed to Reaction II, since the reaction can be expected to take place almost concurrently with the first. Moreover, the multiple peaks observed would be caused by the slightly different volatilization temperatures of the various solid solutions formed, possibly derived from one another. If the solid solution is not formed then a single peak should have been observed corresponding to a finite volatilization temperature of the particular composition formed from Reaction I.

Also the direct variation of the relative intensity of this second group of peaks with that of the first peak is to be expected only if this group of peak is due to Reaction II which would be directly proportional to the amount of the decomposition product formed in Reaction I. Reaction III on the contrary, would vary with the amount of undecomposed Tl_2O_3 and therefore be inversely proportional to Reaction I. The third peak is therefore attributed to Reaction III.

Initially Reaction III was thought to be due to the volatilization of the undecomposed solid Tl_2O_3 . Subsequent visual observations made in separate experiments, have shown that solid Tl_2O_3 melts at about 720° , and boils at about 820° , hence this third peak is attributed to the volatilization (boiling) of the residual molten thallic oxide. This would be consistent with the fairly reproducible temperatures at which this third peak occurs.

In order to confirm these deductions, visual observations were made, as Tl_2CO_3 and Tl_2O_3 (III) were heated from room temperature to 1000° at $6^\circ/\text{min}$. These observations are summarized in Table II.

It is concluded that at high temperatures and in air, the thallic oxide melts and boils off besides undergoing normal decomposition to a lower oxide or oxides. The extent to which the particular reaction predominates depends upon the experimental conditions, important amongst which are the heating rate, the crucible material and

* Since the amount of Tl_2O_3 was not the same in each case the absolute intensities of the peaks are not compared, but only the relative intensities.

the state of dispersion of the sample. These are discussed below.

TABLE II

Visual observations on heating Tl_2CO_3 and Tl_2O_3 separately up to 1000°

Temp. range °C	Tl_2CO_3	Tl_2O_3
200—260°	White powder turns greyish, then brownish giving out sparse white fumes	—
270	melts to black liquid, white fumes evolved	—
330	Liquid spreads over wall of crucible, fumes cease	—
350—400	Uniform black coating (confirmed by X-ray as Tl_2O_3) on inner surface	—
425	Coating slowly creeps to outer wall	—
650	Traces of white fumes begin to be evolved	—
700	White fumes cease, brown fumes appear	Brownish fumes begin to evolve
720	—	Substance melts; vigorous evolution of brown fumes
750	Vigorous evolution of brown fumes [which condense as Tl_2O_3 (confirmed by X-rays)]. Slight indication of melting	
820—900	Substance more or less volatilized	Liquid boils with off continuous evolution of brown fumes
950	Substance completely volatilized.	

Influence of experimental parameters

Effect of the heating rate: It is known⁷ that the rate of heating has a pronounced effect on the T. G. curve and hence on the D.T.G. curve also. In general, faster the heating rate the higher will be the temperatures for (a) inception, (b) apparent maximum and (c) completion of the reaction. Of these, the last two temperatures are usually affected to a much greater extent than the first. The reason for this is that in the specific time required for a reaction to be completed the temperature rise is more, if the heating rate is higher.

The temperature for inception of a reaction should be constant. But here too since there is a small but finite time-interval in which the reaction has to proceed beyond the sensitivity of the thermobalance and recording device, before the weight change becomes noticeable, there is a relatively small effect on the observed temperature of inception of the reaction.

This effect is borne out in all cases (Table I) but is most obvious in case of Tl_2O_3 (III) where there were no preceding reaction to cause any interference. A detailed study of Table I also shows that while the higher heating rates tend to shift the temperatures to higher values, the exact amount of the shift seems to be determined by other factors, such as crucible material, state of dispersion of the sample etc.

7. M. D. Karkhanavala and S. G. Rege, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 459.

The heating rate, not only affects the temperatures of the reaction maxima etc., but can also effect the reactions themselves. In the present case, the slower rate of heating permits the first decomposition reaction to proceed more fully and leave less Tl_2O_3 for direct volatilization. This is best illustrated in the behaviour of Tl_2O_3 (I) (Fig. 2B). In other cases this effect is to some extent masked (a) by the presence of ThO_2 in Tl_2O_3 (II) and (b) by sintering in Tl_2O_3 (III). Hence the heating rate is an important parameter and for T. G. analysis slower rates of heating should be preferred.

Effect of the crucible material: It can be seen from Table I that for the same heating rate, the temperatures for D. T. G. peaks tend to be higher with platinum crucibles than with alumina crucibles. Yet the temperatures of inception and completion of the overall reaction are not markedly affected by a change of the crucible material.

Also, where the material gets finely dispersed and tends to attach to the crucible walls the reaction maxima are brought out more prominently with alumina than with platinum crucibles. Thus for a given heating rate the first decomposition maxima is more prominent for alumina crucibles (figs. 2-4).

Effect of the state of dispersion: It has already been pointed out that visual observations had shown that in Tl_2O_3 (I) as a result of the preceding reaction, the material is spread out as a fine coating on the inner and even the outer wall of the crucible. This was confirmed in actual T. G. runs also, by lifting the furnace at the appropriate temperature.

Because of this fine dispersion, almost the entire weight loss from Tl_2O_3 (I) is by reactions I and II and only a small fraction by reaction III [as can be seen from the extremely small peak at 805° (fig. 2B)].

In contrast, Tl_2O_3 (III) which had not suffered any *in situ* decomposition prior to the final weight loss and which by 700° had sintered to a fairly dense mass, showed weak peaks due to reaction I & II, but very strong peaks for reaction III. This is because the initial decomposition and the subsequent volatilization of the decomposition product was essentially restricted to the exposed surface layer and the bulk remained as Tl_2O_3 .

In the case of Tl_2O_3 (II), the presence of the unreactive ThO_2 modified the behaviour of the Tl_2O_3 , which was somewhat entrapped by the ThO_2 . As a result there was only a little deposit of Tl_2O_3 on the walls of the crucible when the Tl_2CO_3 decomposed and reoxidised to Tl_2O_3 . Hence, here also reaction I and therefore reaction II are somewhat retarded, while reaction III is enhanced.

From this study a few observations on the application and use of thermogravimetry can be made. Direct thermograms are not adequate for elucidating the chemical reactions taking place, and it seems essential that differential thermograms must be obtained. Further, in order to confirm the proposed reaction steps thermograms and subsequent D.T.G. plots must be obtained for at least two heating rates. Also where decomposition and volatilization reactions are involved, the relatively pervious or impervious nature of the surface of the crucibles could play an important role and hence this factor must also be considered while interpreting the results.